

Figure 1

A

- Surrounding normal human tissue
- CCA human tissue

B

- Well and moderately -differentiated CCA
- Poorly-differentiated CCA

C

- Surrounding normal human tissue
- CCA human tissue

Figure 2

A

- Surrounding normal human tissue
- CCA human tissue

B

TGR5
(mRNA microarray: whole tissue)

- | Anatomical location | Perineural invasion |
|---------------------|---------------------|
| ○ Perihilar CCA | ○ Negative |
| ● Intrahepatic CCA | ● Positive |

C

- Surrounding normal human tissue
- CCA human tissue

Figure 3

A

B

Figure 4

A

Figure 4

B

Figure 4

C

Figure 5

A

Figure 5

B

Figure 5

C

Figure 5

D

Figure 5

E

Figure 5

F

Figure 6

A

Figure 6

B

Figure 6

C

Suplemmentary figures

Supplementary Figure 1

Supplementary Figure 2

Supplementary Figure 3

Supplementary Figure 4

